

Jansen, A., Leborgne, F., Wang, Q., & Zhang, C. (2024, May). Contextualizing the “Why”: The Potential of Using Visual Map As a Novel XAI Method for Users with Low AI-literacy. In *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1-7).

Official published version available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3613905.3650812>.
Open access version available at: <https://research.tue.nl/en/publications/contextualizing-the-why-the-potential-of-using-visual-map-as-a-no>.